

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The implications of classical and operant conditioning theories to teaching in Benin EFL intermediate classes

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Abstract

The current research work investigates the implication of Classical and Operant conditioning in teaching English as a foreign language in Benin EFL intermediate classes. It aims at demonstrating how the implication of classical and operant conditioning can help in teaching EFL and its importance in the teaching and learning process. To achieve this goal, samples of EFL learners were tested. The data from the test was submitted to a two-sample independent t-test for the mean to check the impact of the conditioning theories on language development. Moreover, questionnaires were addressed to English as a foreign language teachers and classroom observation was also conducted. Some EFL teachers were interviewed as well. The results from data collected show that the implication of conditioning theories has a positive impact in EFL teaching and learning. They also show that EFL teachers recognize the usefulness of the classical and operant conditioning in the teaching and learning process. Classical and operant conditioning are paramount learning theories which can be applied by teachers to overcome learners' obstacles in learning English as a foreign language.

Keywords: Classical Conditioning; Operant Conditioning; Teaching EFL

1. Introduction

Language learning is an active process that begins at birth and continues throughout life. According to Watson, learning is a process of interaction between stimulus and response (Cited in Johnson, 2001). It is also the way people develop the ability to communicate in a second or foreign language. Language is a means of communication in the society. It is a tool for learning and the most important medium through which knowledge is acquired. According to Oyinloye (2004), language is a method by which a person expresses his thoughts and feelings in such a way that the person can be understood by others. Language refers to that specific human possession which is used for communication in the society. These few words show the necessity of mastering language and translate well enough Benin learners' drive to understand particularly English knowing its importance in world communication. This sets the framework for learning English as a foreign language as Benin has French as second language, which calls for effective teaching.

For school psychologists, no effective learning happens without the theories that govern teaching/ learning. In the context of EFL, they are the main tools in the process of the teaching and learning of the language. Such theories include the behaviorist classical and operant conditioning this research focuses on. Other theories are cognitivism and constructivism. With the implementation of these, EFL learning in Benin should roll. Learners should demonstrate the ability to describe experiences and give simple opinions. They should be able to follow clear and slow speeches, and understand simplified articles like BBC English learning programs. Their ability should also be noted in drafting texts. All this with three- or four-years' language learning experience, which will get them labelled as intermediate.

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Unfortunately, a large number of EFL learners are still unable to communicate in English language despite the recent government reforms and investments (Iwikotan, 2016, p.59). There are learners in intermediate classes who follow an intermediate program but whose mastery of English are all but intermediate. Many reasons can be blamed for the fact. Hindémé (2019, p.36) identifies the lack of qualified teachers among others. Teachers' lack of qualifications gets their knowledge and mastery of the theories governing teaching/ learning questioned. In case they do know and master the theories, their effective implication of these in their teaching to induce acquisition and sustained learning may be questioned as well. A failure in this will always result in the poor communication skills of the learners.

Purpose of the Study

This research intends to show that the classical and operant conditioning can allow Benin EFL teachers to induce language acquisition and strengthen their learners' motivation to learn English. For that aim, the first goal set is to shed light on the impact of the classical and operant conditioning on the learners' language acquisition and motivation to learn. Secondly, how the implication of classical and operant conditioning can help in teaching English as foreign language will be seen. The third goal is to show the importance of classical and operant conditioning in EFL intermediate classes. The fourth goal is to know the perception of Benin EFL teachers about the implication of classical and operant conditioning to enhance students' academic performance in English language learning (ELL).

1.1. Research Questions

The following questions have been established for this research study.

- What impact do the classical and operant conditioning have on learners' language development?
- What is the importance of classical and operant conditioning in intermediate EFL classes?
- How can the implication of classical and operant conditioning help in teaching English as foreign language?
- What is the perception of Beninese EFL teachers about the implication of classical and operant conditioning on students' academic performance in English Language Learning (ELL)?

1.2. Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have also been established for this research study

- Ho₁: Classical and operant conditioning have a negative impact on the development of English EFL learners in Benin.
- Ho₂: Classical and operant conditioning are not important in intermediate English classes.
- Ho₃: Classical and operant conditioning do not help in the teaching of EFL.
- Ho₄: EFL teachers have a negative perception about the implication of Classical and operant conditioning in the teaching of EFL in intermediate classes.

2. Literature review

Several scholars and senior have already worked in the domain of Classical and Operant Conditioning

2.1. Brief History of Classical and Operant Conditioning

2.1.1. Pavlov's Classical Conditioning

Classical conditioning is a process that Pavlov discovered through experiments on dogs. Based on the assumption that by using certain stimuli, human behavior can be changed according to what is desired, Pavlov conducted experiments using animals (dogs). He thinks animals have some senses in common with humans. He was experimenting on how to conduct surgery on a dog's cheek. He noticed that when shown some food, the dogs drool. Now, before feeding the dogs, he presented them with red light first. He remarked that upon repetition of the process, at one time by just showing the red light without any food, the dogs drool anyway. He concluded that the food is reasonable stimulus, while the red light is artificial stimulus. The event is called: Conditional or Conditioned reflex response. That was the discovery of classical conditioning which could be understood as the fact that a neutral stimulus repeatedly paired with a conditioning stimulus gives rise to a desired reaction.

The experiments performed by Pavlov and other experts were affected by the views of behaviorism, in which the symptoms of a person's psychology like anxiety, phobias or compulsions rather than be seen as signs of hidden mental processes are considered as learned behaviors. They are, in behaviorist terms, observable responses to environmental stimuli. Following these principles, classical conditioning seeks to change the observed behavior as a whole by means of two types of stimuli triggering response. The two types of stimuli are the unconditioned stimulus (unconditioned stimulus - UCS), which automatically generates a stimulus that precedes the response without any learning. For example a bell, a previously neutral stimulus, eventually brings a conditioned response after being associated with an unconditioned stimulus in the example of food. The bell rings each time the food is to be presented.

2.1.2. Skinner's Theory of Operant Conditioning

Operant conditioning was first described by behaviorist B.F. Skinner, which is why you may occasionally hear it referred to as Skinnerian conditioning. As a behaviorist, Skinner believed that it was not really necessary to look at internal thoughts and motivations in order to explain behavior. Instead, he suggested that we should look only at the external, observable causes of human behavior. Through the first part of the 20th century, behaviorism became a major force within psychology. The ideas of John B. Watson dominated this school of thought early on. Watson focused on the principles of classical conditioning, once famously suggesting that he could take any person regardless of their background and train them to be anything he chose. Early behaviorists focused on associative learning. Skinner was more interested in how the consequences of people's actions influenced their behavior.

Skinner used the term operant to refer to any *"active behavior that operates upon the environment to generate consequences."* Skinner's theory explains how we acquire the range of learned behaviors we exhibit every day. His theory was heavily influenced by the work of psychologist Edward Thorndike, who had proposed what he called the law of effect. According to this principle, actions that are followed by desirable outcomes are more likely to be repeated while those followed by undesirable outcomes are less likely to be repeated. Operant conditioning relies on a fairly simple premise: Actions that are followed by reinforcement will be strengthened and more likely to occur again in the future. If a teacher tells a funny story in class and everybody laughs, she/he will probably be more likely to tell more funny stories in the future. If a student raises his hand to ask a question and his teacher praises his polite behavior, the student will be more likely to raise his hand the next time the teacher has a question or comment. As the behavior was followed by reinforcement, or a desirable outcome, the preceding action is strengthened.

2.2. Meaning of Classical and Operant Conditioning

2.2.1. Meaning of Classical Conditioning

Classical conditioning, Pavlovian conditioning or respondent conditioning is a process in which a stimulus that was previously neutral, as the sound of a bell, comes to evoke a particular response, as salivation, by being repeatedly paired with another stimulus that normally evokes the response, as the taste of food. In other words, it is a process of changing behavior by associating completely meaningless element with meaningful ones.

2.2.2. Meaning of Operant Conditioning

Skinner called his theory operant conditioning as it is based on certain operations or actions which an organism has to carry out. The term 'operant' stresses that behavior operates upon the environment to generate its own consequences. An operant is a set of acts which conditions an organism in doing something. In the process of operant conditioning operant responses are modified or changed by reinforcement.

2.3. How does Classical Conditioning Work in classroom?

Existing literature sees Classical conditioning play different roles in the classroom setting. It creates positive classroom associations. Teachers can pair English learning with pleasant stimuli (smiles, praise, games, and music). Example: If a student consistently hears encouraging feedback when speaking English, they begin to feel positive emotions whenever they use the language. Classical Conditioning also reduces anxiety (Deconditioning). Many learners feel fear or nervousness when speaking English.

Teachers can gradually pair speaking tasks with non-threatening, supportive contexts, helping students overcome negative emotional reactions. Example: A shy learner who dreads oral presentations can start with short, fun role-plays in pairs before moving to group presentations. In addition, Classical Conditioning Establishes Classroom Routines.

Using signals (like a bell, hand clap, or phrase in English) consistently before an activity can condition students to respond automatically. Example: Saying "Let's get started!" always at the beginning of class conditions learners to settle

down and pay attention. Repetitive stimulus–response exercises (like teacher says a word, students repeat) rely on conditioning to build automatic pronunciation habits. Associating rules and discipline with predictable teacher responses. Example: Students who consistently hear a polite English phrase like “Please sit down” (instead of scolding) may associate classroom order with calm, respectful language use. Finally, Classical Conditioning builds Cultural Familiarity. Teachers can pair English with cultural symbols (songs, films, food) so learners associate the language with enjoyable cultural experiences.

2.4. The Components of Classical Conditioning

2.4.1. Neutral Stimulus

A stimulus which initially produces no specific response other than focusing attention. Example; you hear a car horn, but you live in the city so its catches attention but it is normal. Sarah, (2006) states:

Stimulus is all that is given by the teacher to the learner, while the response is in the form of students’ reactions or responses to the stimulus given by the teacher. Processes that occur between stimulus and response cannot be observed and cannot be measured.

Through this assertion, Sarah pointed out how stimulus works on students and the difference between stimulus and response.

2.4.2. Unconditional Stimulus (UCS)

Any stimulus that can evoke a response without the organism going through any previous learning. Example; when you smell your favorite food and automatically feel hungry.

2.4.3. Unconditioned Response (UCR)

The unlearned response that occurs naturally in reaction to the unconditioned stimulus. Example; jerking back your hand after touching something hot.

2.4.4. Conditioned Stimulus (CS)

A previously neutral stimulus that after association with an unconditioned stimulus eventually comes to trigger a conditioned response. Example: at first, when you ring a bell, it elicits no response with a dog but after a while the dog learns that the bell means food, the bell becomes a conditioned stimulus.

2.4.5. Conditioned Response (CR)

An automatic response established by training to an ordinarily neutral stimulus. Example: The sound of a can opener or bag being opened can trigger excitement in an animal. If your pet is accustomed to being fed after hearing the sound of a can or bag being opened, he or she might become very excited whenever they hear that sound. This behavior is a conditioned response.

2.5. The Components of Operant Conditioning

2.5.1. Positive Reinforcement

Positive reinforcement is based on the principle that the frequency of a response increases because it is followed by a stimulus that contains award. According to Seng, et.al (2009:211) "*a positive reinforcer adds desirable stimuli to a behavioral event in the hope that the event will increase in strength*".

2.5.2. Negative Reinforcement

Negative reinforcement is based on the principle that the frequency of a response increases because it is followed by a stimulus that is not fun to be removed. According to Seng, et.al (2009:212) "*responses that are followed by the escape from or removal of an undesirable situation are likely to be repeated and constitute negative reinforcement*".

Thus, the negative reinforcement is meant to strengthen the behavior which is expected to increase due to be the removal of an unpleasant stimulus. Example, learners and teachers often ask and answer questions eliminating criticisms to increase their level of confidence. If the teacher does not negatively criticize the learners, they will feel confident in asking questions. Thus, the behavior that you want to repeat or enhance is the possibility of frequent

questions and the unpleasant stimulus you need to remove is the criticism of the teacher so that students are not shy and will often ask questions because the teacher does not criticize the unqualified / deviating (Baum, 2005; Pierce and Cheney, 2013).

2.5.3. Punishment

Punishment is defined as the opposite of reinforcement since it is designed to weaken or eliminate a response rather than increase it. It is an aversive event that decreases the behavior that it follows. According to Santhrock (2009:238) "*punishment is a consequence that decreases the probability that a behavior will occur.*"

Like reinforcement, punishment can work either by directly applying an unpleasant stimulus; like a shock after a response or by removing a potentially rewarding stimulus, for instance, deducting someone's pocket money to punish undesirable behavior.

2.6. Key difference between Classical and Operant Conditioning.

The main difference between classical conditioning and instrumental conditioning is that classical conditioning involves involuntary behavior, whereas instrumental conditioning involves voluntary behavior. Both classical conditioning and instrumental conditioning are two types of associative learning processes, which involve learning about the relationship between two stimuli. Classical conditioning is a learning process that occurs by linking two stimuli together to produce a new learned response in an individual, while instrumental conditioning is a learning process that occurs by linking behavior and a consequence for that behavior. (Cherry, K. 2014). The following table sums up the key difference between classical and operant conditioning:

Table 1 Comparison of key Differences between Classical and Operant Conditioning

Classical Conditioning	Operant Conditioning
Discovered by Pavlov	Discovered by Skinner
Classical conditioning is a learning process that occurs by linking two stimuli together to produce a new learned response in an individual	Operant conditioning is a learning process that occurs by linking a behavior and a consequence for that behavior
Involves involuntary behavior (reflex action). In other words, it connects an involuntary response to a neutral stimulus	Involves voluntary behavior. In other words, it encourages a behavior by pairing it with a consequence
Stimulus comes first. That means that a signal is given before the reflect	Behavior comes first. That means that reinforcement or punishment is given after the behavior
A neutral stimulus becomes a conditioned stimulus through association with an unconditioned stimulus and elicits a conditioned response	Probability of a certain behavior occurring is altered by consequences following it

2.6.1. Critical view about the literature

Going through the existing literature, it clearly appears that the conditioning theories can not only be used in education but they can be quite useful in the teaching and learning of EFL. The use of classical conditioning for creating positive classroom associations, reducing anxiety, establishing classroom routines, pronunciation and repetition drills, behavior management and building cultural familiarity has been discussed. The use of operant conditioning for reinforcement has been proved. While all this works for a good classroom environment and the nurturing of learners' motivation to learn, little has been said about their use for vocabulary acquisition and constant practice. This research sets itself the goal of looking into the impact classical conditioning can have on the learners' language acquisition, which can be strengthened by the desire instilled by operant conditioning. As a matter of fact, during a vocabulary class, for example, the teacher can help the learners on the word pronouncing, a neutral stimulus, and then associate the sound with the pictures of what the words serve to call. Repetition of the practice may condition the learners to easily guess what the words stand for without the need to be shown a picture. This could be done for some other language patterns that may serve as templates. Once this acquisition happens, it can be strengthened by the use of operant conditioning for more sustained improvement with the learners. Classical and operant conditioning could thus be applied not only for favoring

classroom atmosphere but also for effective language learning. They could then help to make a difference. There is the ambition of this research.

3. Design and Methodology of the Research

This chapter describes the methodology used to collect data during the investigation. It contains five points which are: research design, target population and sampling, the different research instruments, the procedure of data collection and data analysis.

3.1. Research Design

The research is done along a mixed approach. It follows a quantitative and qualitative design to first check if the implication of classical and operant conditioning really makes a difference in EFL learning with intermediate learners and then see how it can be used to improve the proficiency of those learners.

3.2. Target Population and Sampling

The research targets the EFL intermediate learners of CEG₂ Adjarra especially the learners of 3e, which makes an overall population size of 171 participants for its quantitative aspect. From this will be drawn a representative sample which will be supplemented by a number of teachers to make up the sample from which qualitative data will be collected.

In order to reach a representative sample Solvin's formula has been resorted to with 95% level of confidence, which matches 5% margin of error. This allows the definition of a sample of 120 participant learners, representative of the overall 171 learners' population. This number has been split in two, that is, two groups of 60 participant learners making two independent groups or samples from which relevant data will be collected for the hypothesis testing. They are supplemented by 10 teachers chosen on a purposive sampling basis.

3.2.1. Research Instruments and their Validity

Reliable instruments for data collection have been designed and pre-testing has been conducted to check their validity. These instruments are: a test paper, questionnaires, interviews, and classroom observations. With the authorization from the officials of the school, the EFL teachers have been met, especially those in charge of the intermediate classes. They have been informed of the study and its aim. Their active participation has been required and classical and operant conditioning theories have been discussed with them to make sure they are aware of them. Through them, the participant learners have been reached. It was agreed with the teachers that one teaches a group of participant learners without the principles of conditioning while another applies the principles with the other group. The teacher have been followed on a two-weeks class with the learners on the same themes after which the learners have been submitted to the test to see what development they have achieved.

3.2.2. Hypothesis Testing

A two-sample independent test for the mean has been conducted to judge the impact of the conditioning theories on the language development of the learners.

3.2.3. Questionnaire, Interviews and Classroom Observations

The study included a questionnaire devoted to EFL teachers. It was composed of nine (09) questions. Interviews were used to check the results of the questionnaire. During the investigation, two (02) teachers were randomly selected and interviewed. After the interviews, some EFL teachers were observed in classroom situation. Two classes of 3^{ème} and two classes of 4^{ème} were involved in this research study. The observations helped to check to what extent teachers implement Classical and Operant conditioning their classes while teaching English as a foreign language to intermediate learners. Finally, the researcher compared the results of the two classroom observations with the results collected from questionnaire and interviews.

4. Presentation and discussion of the Results

This chapter deals with the presentation of the results of the different investigations which include interviews and questionnaires to EFL teachers and the discussion of the results.

4.1. Presentation of the Results

The data collected for the study were analyzed to provide answers to the research questions that guide the study. First will be presented the data from the test and results from the hypothesis testing. Then, will come the data from the questionnaire, interviews and observations.

4.1.1. Impact of the Classical and Operant Conditioning on Learners' Language Development

- Participants:
- Sample 1: 60
- Sample 2: 60

4.2. Data from the test

Table 2 Participant learners' grades

Grades]0-5[[5-10[[10-15[[15-20[
Number from Sample 1	11	29	15	5
Number from Sample 2	0	25	30	15

The table shows the different grades the participant learners from the two independent samples have got after the testing. The grades have been given by range of five with 10 as average grade. It could be seen that sample 2 made of learners taught with the implication of the conditioning theories presents better grades than Sample 1 made of learners taught without the implication of the theories. The trend will be confirmed by the data from the descriptive statistics.

4.3. Descriptive Statistics

Table 3 Statistics of the two samples

	Sample 1	Sample 2
Mean	8.13	13.3
Std. Deviation	3.53	2.68
Minimum	3	7
Maximum	16	18

The data shows that sample 1 presents a lower mean than sample 2 with greater distance between the grades as standard deviation for the sample is higher than that of sample 2. Not only the mean of sample 2 is higher but it also counts higher grades with minimum and maximum grades higher than those of sample 1.

4.4. The Hypothesis Testing

Independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare the variable in Sample 1 and Sample 2.

Table 4 The independent test results

	t	df	p	Cohen's d
Equal variances	-9.04	118	<.001	1.65
Unequal variances	-9.04	109.99	<.001	1.65

As it could be seen that the calculated test statistic is $t = -9.04$, which in absolute value is large. This translates that the difference between the groups' means is far greater than what would be expected if the null hypothesis were true. The consistency between the values of the degrees of freedom either for equal variances (118) or unequal variances (109.99) also leads to the same conclusion. All this added to the p value which is less than 0.1% ($p < 0.001$) makes it possible to reject the null hypothesis.

It can then be said that rather than have a negative impact on the learners' skills development, the implication of classical and operant conditioning does make a difference between the performance of the groups of learners. It can then be resorted to by EFL teachers to help in the language development of their learners.

4.5. Importance of Classical and Operant Conditioning for EFL Teaching:

4.5.1. Responses from Teachers

Teacher's Qualifications

The results have indicated that ten percent (10%) of the teachers have been teaching with CAPES (Degree obtained at the training college to teach professionally). Twenty percent (20%) of teachers have been teaching with a Bachelor's degree, thirty percent (30%) have been doing the teaching job with a Master's and forty percent (40%) of them are trained with BAPES degree. This result showed that few of the questioned teachers were professionally qualified.

Teachers' Years of Teaching

The findings revealed that seventy percent (70%) of teachers said that they had more than five years of experience, ten percent (10%) of them point on less than five years of experience whereas, twenty percent (20%) of them asserted that their time of teaching is about five years. It proves that most of teachers can say a word about the current topic.

Teachers' Opinion about TEFL Difficulties

Ninety percent of teachers declared that TEFL difficulties were not easy to raise whereas ten percent (10%) of teachers claimed that the difficulties of TEFL were easy to raise and none of them believed that TEFL had any difficulty.

Teachers' way of Teaching English Language in Classroom

Ten percent (10%) of teachers said that they had been implicating some learning theories while teaching English language in the class whereas ninety percent (90%) of teachers confessed that they considered curriculum and none of them revealed that they were maximizing Teacher's Talking Time. This leads to the conclusion that the majority of EFL teachers rules the course by considering only the curriculum.

Teachers' Opinion about the impact of operant and classical conditioning on EFL intermediate learners

Figure 1 Teachers' Opinion about the impact of the two theories on EFL intermediate learners

As far as figure 1 is concerned, one hundred percent (100%) of teachers confessed that operant and classical conditioning can have positive impact on EFL intermediate learners whereas, none of them defended the contrary. This implies that all the questioned teachers recognize the positive impact of learning theories on EFL intermediate learners.

Teachers' Opinion about the importance of the implication of operant and classical conditioning in teaching EFL

Figure 2 Teachers' Opinion towards the importance of implication of operant and classical conditioning in teaching EFL

The result from this figure 2 indicated that eighty percent (80%) of teachers recognized that the implication of operant and classical conditioning was important in foreign language learning and teaching whereas, twenty percent (20%) of them defended the contrary. The majority of the teachers recognized the great importance of learning theories in EFL intermediate classroom.

The Ways Teachers Congratulate their Students' Best Reactions

Table 5 Teachers' Ways of Congratulating Students' Best Reactions

The Ways Teachers Congratulate their Students' Best Reactions	Frequency	Percentage (%)
By giving her/him mark	02	20
By encouraging him with applaud	07	70
By praising her/him	01	10
Total	10	100

Table 4 shows the ways teachers congratulate their students. From the analysis, seventy percent (70%) of teachers said that they congratulated students by encouraging them with applaud, twenty percent (20%) confessed that they encouraged students by giving them marks and ten percent of teachers said that they praised students when they reacted well. Based on this result the majority of teachers encouraged their students with "Applaud", which created "reinforcement" of students' capacity.

4.5.2. Impact of Teachers' Congratulations on Students Upcoming Reactions

Figure 3 The Impact of Teachers Congratulations' on Students Upcoming Reactions

Figure 3 revealed that the whole population of teachers which was hundred percent (100%) confirmed that the way they congratulated their students had positive impact on their upcoming reactions. None of the teachers said the contrary. According to all the teachers, congratulations make "positive reinforcement" on students' capacity to more involve in the learning process.

Teachers' Perception about the Implication of some Learning Theories to Teaching English as Foreign Language

Table 6 Teachers' Perception toward the Implication of some Learning Theories to Teaching EFL

Teachers' Perception about the Implication of some Learning Theories to Teaching EFL	Frequency	Percentage (%)
It can help students to be more involved in the learning process	02	20
It can help students in language acquisition	07	70
It can increase the students' performances	01	10
Total	10	100

Through the table 5, twenty percent (20%) of teachers justified that learning theories can help students to be more involved in the learning process, seventy percent (70%) of teachers confirmed that learning theories can help students in their language acquisition and ten percent (10%) of teachers had the feeling that learning theories could increase students' performance. From this result, it could be inferred that the implication of learning theories helps students to acquire rapidly new language.

4.5.3. Classroom Observation Report

The overall aim of the observation was in essence to reveal the way English language was taught as well as students' engagement on it. As a matter of fact, the classroom observation divulged a lot about the English language teaching on the side of the teachers and likewise about English language learning on the students' side.

Indeed, several EFL teachers had been teaching English language by basing on curriculum. For that point, it should be said that they are not aware of which theories they apply in their classes let alone judge by themselves if those theories could help them reach their goals.

I can say that they do not even think about implicating some learning theories to their teaching job because they think that implication of learning theories in teaching is waste of the time.

4.5.4. Interview Report

I have conducted interviews in order to cross check the results of the questionnaires. The analysis of the different questions asked to teachers shows that teachers are aware of the positive impacts that teaching with learning theories might have on students. The majority of teachers affirmed that learning theories can be helpful to make both students and teachers more interested in learning EFL for the ones and in teaching EFL for the others.

However, few of the teachers showed their disagreement with implicating learning theories to teaching English as a Foreign Language. For them, the implication of learning theories in classroom is like a kind of time wasting. They think that implicating learning theories in the teaching process is a long series of protocol which can take more time in their time schedule. Due to that fact, those teachers prefer to focus their student's attention only on their English textbook (Document d'accompagnement).

5. Discussion of the Findings

The discussion of the findings turns around the three research questions stated in chapter one.

5.1. How the Implication of Classical and Operant Conditioning helps in teaching English as Foreign Language

Classical and operant conditioning were suitable to be applied in the classroom in teaching English as Foreign Language (EFL). It could be alternative way to improve students in learning English language. In this study, several things have been deduced. Firstly, for some EFL teachers, they were inclined to have similar problem; they could not implicate the

right learning theories to their teaching process, they could not find the correct methods of teaching EFL, after that some of them got difficulties to categorize the kind of teaching theories and methods such as in materials in shopping list.

All these can be explained by the teachers' professional and academic qualifications as it is mentioned in the result of figure 1 which shows that ten percent (10%) of the teachers have been teaching with CAPES degree, twenty percent (20%) of teachers have been teaching with a bachelor's degree, thirty percent (30%) have been doing the teaching job with Master's and forty percent (40%) of them are trained with BAPES degree. This result leads to the conclusion that the majority of EFL teachers in CEG₂ Adjarra do not have the required professional qualification to teach in Secondary Schools.

Secondly, subjects in experimental class showed students' big desire in the learning process. For instance, they were active to give some correct answers to their teacher's questions. They were also active when teacher delivered his course, especially when the course is based on vocabulary. Going from the control group taught without any regards to classical and operant conditioning to the experimental group taught considering these theories, it can be kept from this results that not only the learning atmosphere but the learning itself was positively impacted. Words were easily acquired without much effort due to the repletion of the process and the improvement made was motivation enough for more improvement sustained by the implication of operant conditioning. On the other hand, in the control group taught with no regards for classical and operant conditioning, the students' mastery and behaviors were very different. Most of the students were in fairly good score. That means that, the implication of classical and operant conditioning helps to raise students' level as far as learning English as foreign language and academic achievement are concerned.

Psychologically speaking, another help of the implication of classical and operant conditioning in teaching English as foreign language has been argued by recent research that, *positive reinforcement motivate daily behavior* (Yusuf and Juntika, 2011:130). It is such that when the students study hard to get good point in class, the reinforcement in operant conditioning influences the students' enthusiasm in learning. This supports the condition in the experimental group in this study. The students in the experimental group were easily learning vocabulary as it is easily and clearly impressed onto them and followed by reinforcement justifying their enthusiasm to learn. They were even not afraid to express other examples related to materials which had been explained to them.

5.2. The importance of Classical and Operant Conditioning in Intermediate EFL Classes

Learning theories remain an important and a basic tool in order to learn and teach a foreign language. They give students as well as teachers access to unlimited amounts of technique and strategies to teach and learn language. That is to say, the more the students and teachers are used to the learning theories, the better they are in learning and teaching language. It is due to that undeniable importance of learning theories to teaching EFL in intermediate classes that hundred percent (100%) of teachers have confessed that operant and classical conditioning are very important and they can have positive impact on teaching English as Foreign Language on intermediate learners whereas, none (0%) of them proved the contrary. This result concludes that all CEG₂ Adjarra EFL teachers recognize the usefulness of classical and operant conditioning to teach English for intermediate learners.

Unfortunately, many teachers see the implication of learning theories in teaching EFL as just another kind of time wasting. In this line, the data shows that just ten percent (10%) of teachers implicate some learning theories while teaching English language in the class whereas ninety percent (90%) of teachers confessed that they consider curriculum and none (0%) of them revealed that they are maximizing Teacher Talking Time. It can be kept from this results that, despite the fact that they all recognize the importance of learning theories, all the questioned CEG₂ Adjarra EFL teachers do not implicate learning theories to teach English in their classes, which could be interpreted as a somewhat ignorance of theirs of the true significance of the learning theories.

5.3. The Perception of Benin EFL Teachers about the two theories

Finding out the perception of Benin EFL teachers about the implication classical and operant conditioning theories means checking the most efficient learning theories to improve and enhance students' academic performance in English Language. It is noteworthy that the majority of teachers are aware that learning theories can be helpful to make students more interested in learning EFL and teachers in teaching EFL. In other words, teachers have seen classical and operant theories as appropriate as any other theories to teach EFL than other theories. The data shows that forty percent (40%) of teachers justify that learning theories can help students to be more involved in the learning process, fifty percent (50%) of teachers confirmed that learning theories can help students in their language acquisition and ten percent (10%) of teachers think that learning theories can increase students' performance. It can be concluded that all the EFL teachers of CEG₂ Adjarra have different perception of the implication of classical and operant conditioning in students' academic performance in English Language Teaching. While some of them think that learning theories can help students

to be more involved in the learning process, some of them supported that learning theories can help students in their language acquisition, another part of the teachers confirmed that learning theories can increase students' performance. Those points are supported by all CEG2 Adjarra EFL teachers.

6. Conclusion

This research work has investigated the significance of implicating classical and operant conditioning theories to teaching English as foreign. The aim of the current research was to shed light on how the implication of classical and operant conditioning can help in teaching English as foreign language and to show the importance of classical and operant conditioning in intermediate EFL classes. To achieve this goal, I have tried to expand my knowledge about the topic under consideration by reading the books, articles and journals for some senior graduate student teachers interested in the importance of learning theories in EFL intermediate classes, the difficulties teachers and learners encountered related to teaching and learning and the advantages learners can gain from it. So, in order to collect relevant information about this research work, I have administered a testing, questionnaires to EFL teachers and conducted classroom observations. Interviews were also conducted.

The study has provided useful insights into the enhancement of effective teaching and learning of English language through the use of strategies and approaches. It is important to understand that learning theories are important in intermediate classes, and they are also unavoidable in beginner and advanced classes. Classical and operant conditioning reinforce learners' ability on the learning process. So, the reinforcement in operant conditioning influenced the students' enthusiasm in learning English language.

The results from the findings showed that few of the teachers who tended to rule the course with learning theories request positive impact. It can be said that it is one of the strategies teachers could use in order to rouse their learner's motivation. Furthermore, the perception of teachers about learning theories is that, they can be helpful to make students more interested in learning EFL and teachers in teaching EFL.

Therefore, this study attempted to provide more information by investigating classical and operant conditioning and their positive effect on EFL learners' academic achievement. I hope that this study will also make more contribution to researchers aiming to conduct empirical studies in this area.

Given the information above, many researches need to be done to make clear relations among classical and operant conditioning and other learning theories. Range of grades represented can be used as a variable in the model to see how to affect prediction degree of variables. In the research, the total 120 intermediate students are enrolled. To increase the reliability and generalization of study, similar research can be conducted with bigger population and reach good fit values. Different measurement types of stimuli and response can be used as indicators to see their influences on English language learning.

References

- [1] Baum, W.M. (2005). *Understanding Behaviorism: Behavior, Culture and Evolution*. New York: Blackwell.
- [2] Boutelle K. and Bouton M.(2015), Implications of learning theory for developing programs to decrease overeating. *Appetite*.; 93:62-74.doi:10.1016/j.appet.2015.05.013
- [3] Bouton M. (2015) Implications of Learning Theory for Developing Programs to Decrease Overeating. *Appetite*.
- [4] Cherry, (2014). "How Instrumental Conditioning Works According to Psychology." *Very well Mind*.
- [5] Hindémé, U. O. S. (2025). "Learners' Engagement in EFL Classrooms: an Exploration of the Emotional Dimension." *European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*. 9(3): 25-45. www.oapub.org/edu
- [6] Hulac D, Benson N, et al. (2016). Using Variable Interval Reinforcement Schedules to Support Students in the Classroom: An Introduction With Illustrative Examples. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*.; 6(1):90-96.
- [7] Iwilotan, E. (2016). *Critical Appraisal of Secondary School English Curricula in Benin*. Glienicke: Galda Verlag.
- [8] Johnson, K. (2001). *An Introduction to Foreign Language Learning and Teaching*. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.

- [9] Mash, J. W., and Johnston, C. (2008). Parental Social Cognitions: Considerations in the Acceptability of and Engagement in Behavioral Parent Training. *Clin. Child Fam. Psychology*.
- [10] Pierce, W., and Cheney, C., D. (2013). *Behavior Analysis and Learning*, (5th Edition). New York: Psychology Press.
- [11] Oyinloye, C. (2004). *Language Education and Language Teaching Methods*. Ado-Ekiti: Green Line Publisher.
- [12] Rilling M. How the challenge of explaining learning influenced the origins and development of John B.Watson's behaviorism. *Am JPsychol*. 2000; 113(2): 275-301.
- [13] Sarah E. I. (2006). Bending Behavior. *American Scientist*. Research Triangle Park. Vol (94) (3), pp. 267
- [14] Santrock, J.W. (2009). *Educational Psychology*. Fourth Edition: New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [15] Segers E, et al. (2018) Working Memory and Reinforcement Schedule Jointly Determine Reinforcement Learning in Children: Potential Implications for Behavioral Parent Training. *Front Psychol*. 2018;9:394.doi:10.3389/fpsyg.00394.
- [16] Seng, T. et.al (2009). *Educational Psychology*. Singapore: Seng Lee Press.
- [17] Sprouls K, Mathur SR and Upreti G. (2015) Is positive feedback a forgotten classroom practice? Findings and implications for at-risk students. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth*.; 59(3)
- [18] Zwi, M., et al (2011). Parent training interventions for Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) in children aged 5 to 18 years (Review). *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 7:CD003018.doi:10.1002/14651858.CD003018.pub3